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17

PLACENTAL CHORIOANGIOMA

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Introduction:

Placental chorioangioma or placental hemangioma is the most common benign non-trophoblastic tumor. It is derived from the excessive proliferation of small vessels in villous stroma with variable association of stromal solid areas. The estimated incidence of placental chorioangioma is about 1% in microscopely examined placentas. Most chorioangiomas are benign incidental findings, but as size increases, there is an increasing risk of adverse outcome due to high output heart failure (cardiomegaly, polyhydramnios, increased velocity in the middle cerebral artery, fetal hydrops) from arteriovenous shunting, platelet trapping (consumptive coagulopathy), and iatrogenic preterm delivery. In this case report we have presented this rare case of chorioangioma which was diagnosed incidentally on ultrasonography.

Keywords: placental chorioangioma

Case report:

A 21 years old pregnant female 2nd gravida with 32 weeks of gestation presented to us with complains of:

- Excessive abdominal distension for 2 weeks
- Lower abdominal pain with respiratory discomfort for 2 days

The female had a history of one full term normal delivery without peripartum significant events. There was no other significant obstetric, menstrual, past family and personal history.

On examination:

- Vitals were within normal limits
- General examination revealed pitting edema in bilateral lower limbs extending up to medial malleolus
- Respiratory rate 24/min
- Rest general examination was within normal limits

Obstetric examination

- Skin: marked stria gravidarum
- P/A: grossly enlarged
- Fundal height was more than gestational age.
- The uterus was irritable

- fetal heart rate which was 144 /min.
- Per vaginal examination: revealed 2 cm dilated and early effaced cervix with intact membrane.

Workup

All routine blood investigations including Complete blood counts, blood biochemistries and glucose tolerance test were normal.

USG

- 1) single live fetus with 32 weeks of gestation and without structural malformations and hydrops
- 2) Amniotic fluid index of 42 cm and single deep vertical pocket of 13 cm
- 3) hyperechoic mass of 8.5 *6.5cm on placental surface, near cord insertion with hypervascularity, separate from surrounding placental tissue suggestive of placental chorioangioma
- 4) normal fetal Doppler and estimated fetal weight was 1.6kg.

After corticosteroids the therapeutic amniocentesis was done but again, she developed gross polyhydramnios after 4 days of amniocentesis. She had spontaneous preterm normal labor and delivered 1.7kg live baby without peripartum complications to both. As the neonate was low birth weight it was admitted to NICU and was discharged after a week without complications.

Placental Histopathology

1. Macroscopic examination: There was a specimen of a single placenta measuring 24 *18*3 cm with attached cord and membrane. It had one well circumscribed, nodular mass is identified on fetal surface measuring 10*9*3.5 cm. The cut surface is brownish white, hemorrhagic and solid. The mass is well demarcated from adjacent placental disc tissue suggestive of chorioangioma.
2. Microscopic examination: Sections from nodular mass revealed proliferation of capillary sized vascular channels with endothelial cells, hemorrhagic and focal area of calcifications. No other significant pathology in placenta, cord and membrane were found.

Discussion:

Neoplasms of placenta is classified in to two groups i.e., Trophoblastic and non-trophoblastic. Non trophoblastic tumors are common and benign ones include chorioangioma and teratoma. Chorioangioma was first diagnosed by Clarke in 1798. Small chorioangiomas are present in 1% of examined placenta while tumors reaching clinically evident dimension are relatively uncommon. Mostly tumors are discovered only by histology Histologically chorioangioma may be classified into 3 types i.e., vascular, cellular and degenerative. vascular is the most common type of chorioangioma. There can be maternal complications like polyhydramnios, PROM, cervical incompetence, preterm delivery, abruption, malpresentation and PPH. The possible explanations behind polyhydramnios are

- 1) Increased intra vascular pressure caused by blood flow obstruction by a tumor near chord leads to transudation in amniotic cavity.
- 2) Increase transudation may be because of large surface area of tumor.
- 3) Shunting of blood flow into blood vessels of tumor.

There can be fetal complications like congestive cardiac failure, thrombocytopenia, NIH, hemolytic anemia, IUGR, brain infarct, cerebral embolism, IUD, NND.

On USG the differential diagnosis of chorioangioma are:

- 1) Inter villous thrombi - no color flow and surrounded by placental tissues.
- 2) placental hemorrhage - no flow and evolves over time
- 3) Venous lakes - minimum flow and subtle motion
- 4) Gestational trophoblastic disease - cystic, heterogenous mass with abnormal or no fetus in histopathology the differential diagnosis of chorioangioma are chorioangiosis and

Though large chorioangiomas are a rare finding, they can progress to cause a number of fetal and maternal complications which may lead to adverse outcomes in a pregnancy. Timely and proper diagnosis by USG with Doppler can provide a window of opportunity to apply interventions and prevent adverse outcomes.

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